

Additional File 2: Supplementary figures of the manuscript

Figure S1. Transcripts per Million (TPM) distribution identified in oviduct EVs across the bovine estrous cycle.

Figure S2. Comparisons of differential abundant transcripts (DT) among stages (FDR cut-off <0.001). Dendrograms representing results of unsupervised hierarchical clustering (HCL). Rows indicate single transcripts, while columns represent different stages of the estrous cycle compared. Hierarchical cluster analysis showed a clear separation between S2 and S1 (A), between S3 and S1 (B) and between S4 and S1 (C).

Figure S3. Comparative analysis of the small ncRNA across the bovine estrous cycle. Principal Component analysis (PCA) on small ncRNA oviduct EVs content at 4 different stages of the estrous cycle (S1 in yellow; S2 in red, S3 in green and S4 in blue) for the top 1000 small ncRNA for: **A**) All small ncRNA; **B**) ribosomal RNA (rRNA); **C**) transfer RNA (tRNA); **D**) small nucleolar RNA (snoRNA); **E**) microRNA (miRNA) and **F**) other ncRNA.

Figure S4. Comparisons of differential small ncRNA among stages (cut-off FDR < 0.05). Dendrograms representing results of unsupervised hierarchical clustering (HCL). Rows indicate single ncRNA, while columns represent different stages of the estrous cycle compared. Hierarchical cluster analysis showed a clear separation between S3 and S1 (A) and between S4 and S1 (B) for all small ncRNA.

Figure S5. Comparisons of differential rRNA among stages (cut-off FDR < 0.05). Dendrograms representing results of unsupervised hierarchical clustering (HCL). Rows indicate single ncRNA, while columns represent different stages of the estrous cycle compared. Hierarchical cluster analysis showed a clear separation between S3 and S1 (A) and between S4 and S1 (B) for rRNA.

Figure S6. Comparisons of differential miRNA among stages (cut-off FDR < 0.05). Dendrograms representing results of unsupervised hierarchical clustering (HCL). Rows indicate single ncRNA, while columns represent different stages of the estrous cycle compared. Hierarchical cluster analysis showed a clear separation between S3 and S1 (A) and between S4 and S1 (B) for miRNA.

Figure S7. Comparisons of differential tRNA among stages (cut-off FDR < 0.05). Dendrograms representing results of unsupervised hierarchical clustering (HCL). Rows indicate single ncRNA, while columns represent different stages of the estrous cycle compared. Hierarchical cluster analysis showed a clear separation between S3 and S1 (A) and between S4 and S1 (B) for tRNA.

Figure S8. Comparisons of differential snRNA among stages (cut-off FDR < 0.05). Dendrograms representing results of unsupervised hierarchical clustering (HCL). Rows indicate

single ncRNA, while columns represent different stages of the estrous cycle compared. Hierarchical cluster analysis showed a clear separation between S3 and S1 (A) and between S4 and S1 (B) for snRNA.

Figure S9. Comparisons of differential other ncRNA among stages (cut-off FDR < 0.05). Dendrograms representing results of unsupervised hierarchical clustering (HCL). Rows indicate single ncRNA, while columns represent different stages of the estrous cycle compared. Hierarchical cluster analysis showed a clear separation between S3 and S1 (A) and between S4 and S1 (B) for snRNA.

Figure S10. Oviductal EVs RNA isolated by the use of miRNeasy kit. RNA isolated with the miRNeasy kit (Qiagen) was analyzed using capillary electrophoresis with the Agilent RNA 6000 Pico chip (A) and the small RNA chip (B) on an Agilent 2100 Bioanalyzer ®. The y-axis of the electropherograms represents fluorescence units (FU) and the x-axis represents the nucleotide length of the RNA (nt). Peaks at 25 nt (Pico) and 4 nt (small RNA) represent the internal standard, respectively. Data shown represents the 20 samples analyzed for small ncRNA experiment. Results from the small RNA assay (for miRNeasy) showed small RNA profiles in the range of less than 20 to 200 nucleotides, that could correspond to miRNAs (≈ 22 nt), tRNAs ($\approx 60-90$ nt), (snoRNA ($\approx 70-90$ nt), vault RNA ($\approx 80-110$ nt), Y_RNA (84-113 nt), snRNAs ($\approx 63-190$ nt), and small ribosomal RNAs (5S and 5.8 S).

Figure S11.

Oviductal EVs RNA isolated by the use of RNeasy micro kit. RNA was analyzed using capillary electrophoresis with the Agilent RNA 6000 Pico chip on an Agilent 2100 Bioanalyzer®. The y-axis of the electropherograms represents fluorescence units (FU) and the x-axis represents the nucleotide length of the RNA (nt). Peak at 25 nt represents the internal standard. Data shown represents the 20 samples analyzed for mRNA experiment. Results from Pico chip showed the high integrity of RNA, with prominent 18S and 28S rRNA peaks (represented by spikes around 2000 and 4000 nt).

Figure S12. Analysis of RNA-seq coverage and splice junctions. Integrated Genome Viewer (IGV, v.2.4.8) was used to analyze read coverage and spliced reads of a number of selected genes based on the BAM files for 4 replicates of stage 1 and stage 4, respectively. This and the following panels show so-called Sashimi plots. At the bottom the annotated exons of the respective genes are shown in blue (exons=boxes, introns=lines, arrows=direction of the gene).

ANXA2

CIRBP

EEF1A1

EEF1G

GALE

HEBP1

HSP90AA1

OVGP1

PABPN1

RACK1

RPL6

RPS8

